

LOKALE DEFECTRESONANZ: EIN NEUER ANSATZ ZUR DEFEKTERKENNUNG AN FVK

LOCAL DEFECT RESONANCE: A NEW APPROACH TO SENSITIVE IMAGING OF DEFECTS

IN COMPOSITES

I. Solodov

IKT, Institut für Kunststofftechnik der Universität Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 32, 70569 Stuttgart
Tel.: + 49 (0) 711 68562835, Fax: + 49 (0) 711 68562066, E-Mail: igor.solodov@ikt.uni-stuttgart.de

Kurzfassung: Die in diesem Artikel vorgestellte Methode, die akustische, optische und thermische Defektnachweisempfindlichkeit zu verbessern, indem man die Defekte selektiv mit Ultraschall anregt, basiert auf dem Konzept der lokalen Defektresonanz (LDR). Eine starke Erhöhung der Schwingungsamplitude ermöglicht eine zuverlässige Detektion und Visualisierung eines Schadens, sobald die treibende Ultraschallfrequenz mit der LDR Frequenz übereinstimmt. Dies führt außerdem zu einer stark frequenzselektiven Darstellung, d.h. es bietet sich die Möglichkeit einen bestimmten Defekt unter einer Vielzahl von Defekten zu finden. Mehrere Beispiele veranschaulichen den hohen Anstieg der Sensitivität für optische (Laservibrometrie und Shearografie) und thermografische Methoden und ihre frequenzselektive Defektdarstellung (Flachbodenbohrung, Delaminationen, Risse, Impacts, etc.) für eine Vielzahl von FKV Materialien und Komponenten.

Abstract: In this paper, a consistent way to enhance acoustic, optical and thermal defect responses is suggested by using selective ultrasonic activation of defects based on the concept of Local Defect Resonance (LDR). A strong increase in vibration amplitude at LDR enables to reliably detect and visualize the defect as soon as the driving ultrasonic frequency is matched to the LDR frequency. This also provides a high frequency selectivity of the LDR-based imaging, i.e. an opportunity of detecting a certain defect among a multitude of the other defects in material. Multiple case studies demonstrate a strong increase in sensitivity for both optical (laser vibrometry and shearography) and thermosonic frequency-selective imaging of defects (flat-bottomed holes, delaminations, cracks, impacts, etc.) in a variety of composite materials and components.

Schlagwörter: Lokale Defektresonanz, Ultraschall Thermografie, Ultraschall Shearografie.

Keywords: Local defect resonance, thermosonics, ultrasonic shearography.

Introduction

The efficiency of ultrasonic wave interaction with defects is an important factor, which determines sensitivity and eventually an applicability area of ultrasonic NDT techniques. The outcome of the interaction which is relevant to detection and imaging can be quantified by the amplitude of the defect vibration for a given amplitude of a probing wave. A natural way to increase the vibration amplitude is to drive the specimen at one of its natural frequencies. This approach is used in various ultrasonic NDT techniques including ultrasonic spectroscopy, thermography, and shearography.

The alternative approach to “amplify” vibration of inclusions is used in ultrasonics of bubbles in liquids where a resonance frequency of the bubble is introduced as a key factor to increase an ultrasonic response of the insonified μm -size spheres [1]. The discovery of anomalous nonlinear ultrasonic response of

medical contrast agents made a breakthrough in ultrasonic medical diagnostics.

Likewise, the opportunity of a resonance interaction of ultrasound with defects in solids was theoretically analysed in [2] for plate waves. A direct experimental evidence for resonance vibration located exclusively in the defect area (Local Defect Resonance (LDR)) has been reported by us recently [3]. In this paper, the theoretical background, experimental methodology, and capabilities of LDR ultrasonics are analyzed and applied to enhancing the sensitivity and efficiency of NDT by using laser vibrometry, ultrasonic thermography (thermosonics), and ultrasonic shearography.

Concept of Local Defect Resonance

The concept of LDR is based on the fact that inclusion of a defect leads to a local decrease in stiffness for a certain mass of the material in this area, which should manifest in a particular characteristic frequency of the

defect. The LDR fundamental frequency can be introduced as a natural frequency of the defect with effective rigidity K_{eff} and mass M_{eff} : $f_0 = \sqrt{K_{eff} / M_{eff}} / 2\pi$. To derive the expressions for K_{eff} and M_{eff} one could evaluate potential and kinetic vibration energy of the defect. This approach applied to a circular flat-bottomed hole (FBH) (radius a , thickness h) yields [4]:

$$K_{eff} = 192\pi D / a^2; M_{eff} = 1.8m, \quad (1)$$

where $D = Eh^3 / 12(1 - \nu^2)$ is the bending stiffness and m is the mass of the plate in the bottom of the defect.

Equations (1) are then combined to yield the LDR frequency of the circular FBH:

$$f_0 \approx 1.6h\sqrt{E / 12\rho(1 - \nu^2)} a^4. \quad (2)$$

The problem in practical use of the analytical approach is concerned with the boundary conditions for the defect edges, which were assumed to be clamped in deriving (2). Instead, the finite element simulation by using the software Comsol Multiphysics (physics package “structural dynamics,” “eigenfrequency analysis”) was found to be suitable for analyzing the vibration characteristics of structures with defects and estimation of the LDR frequencies. Figure 1(a) illustrates the vibration pattern at frequency 10.4 kHz, which is readily identified as a fundamental LDR of a circular FBH in a PMMA plate, followed by the higher-order LDR at the higher driving frequency of 23.25 kHz (Fig. 1(b)).

Figure 1. FEM simulations of vibration patterns of a PMMA plate (thickness 3 mm) with a FBH (radius 1 cm, depth 2 mm): fundamental LDR (10.4 kHz) (a), and higher-order LDR (23.25 kHz) (b).

Experimental evidence for LDR

A direct way to experimentally reveal LDR is to measure an individual contribution of each point of the specimen in its overall frequency response in a wide frequency range. For this purpose, an ultrasonic excitation by a wide-band piezoelectric transducer is combined with a laser vibrometer scan of the specimen surface. It enables to probe and indicate all possible resonances in every point of the specimen. The origin of each maximum is then verified by imaging the wave pattern in the specimen at the corresponding frequency. Fig. 2 shows an example of LDR for a circular FBH in a PMMA plate: and the frequency response (a) and the vibration patterns (b-d). A strong enhancement (about 20 dB) of the vibration amplitude with a high Q-factor ($Q \sim 70$) observed locally in the defect area is identified as a fundamental defect resonance (Fig. 2, b). Besides the fundamental LDR, zoom-in scan of the vibration field inside the defect area in a wider frequency range usually reveals the higher-order LDR with multiple nodal lines in the vibration patterns (Fig. 2, c, d).

Figure 2, (a-d). Frequency response (a), fundamental 11 kHz (b) and higher-order LDR vibration patterns for a circular FBH in PMMA plate at different excitation frequencies: (c) mode (0,3) frequency 67.78 kHz, (d) mode (6,2) frequency 75.52 kHz.

LDR defect imaging via laser vibrometry

The methodology of laser vibrometry was successfully applied to a search of LDR in a variety of materials [4] and for imaging of defects. The examples presented in Figs. 3, a, b illustrate a clear evidence of LDR in kHz-frequency range for cracks and impact damage in composite materials and components. Similar LDR with local resonance “amplification” of the vibration amplitude as high as ~ 20 -40 dB were generally measured for other types of realistic defects as illustrated below.

Figure 3. LDR frequency responses (a) and vibration patterns (b) for an impact damage in CFRP plate (top) and a crack in CFRP rod (bottom).

Fig. 4, a, b demonstrates LDR vibration of heat damaged area ($\sim 7 \times 7 \text{ mm}^2$) in carbon fibre-reinforced plastics (CFRP). The ultrasonic excitation at the LDR frequency (48.5 kHz) clearly visualizes the damage (Fig. 4, a) while the image taken at 30 kHz (Fig. 4, b) shows no evidence of the defect.

Figure 4, a, b. LDR imaging of heat damage in CFRP: a) excitation matched to LDR frequency (48.5 kHz); b) 30 kHz excitation.

A strong frequency selectivity of LDR implies a high sensitivity in detecting a certain defect among multitude of the other defects in material. An example of the frequency selective LDR imaging is shown in Fig. 5 for two heat damaged areas in CFRP plate shown in Fig. 5, a. The ultrasonic excitation at the LDR frequencies enables to visualize the defects separately (Fig. 5 b, c) while a frequency sweep within the frequency range of both LDR brings a clear image of all the defects (Fig. 5, d).

If the bandwidth in the frequency sweep mode is expanded beyond the range of the fundamental LDR to include the higher-order resonances, the latter are found to contribute considerably to the quality of imaging. The effect is illustrated in Fig. 6 for a square insert ($2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$) at 1.2 mm depth in a ($300 \times 300 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$) CFRP specimen. While the fundamental LDR vibration pattern (Fig. 6, a) is located mainly in the central part of the defect the maxima of the higher-order reso-

Figure 5, (a-c). Frequency selective LDR imaging of heat damaged areas in CFRP plate (a): separate imaging of defects by matching their LDR frequencies (b-c); imaging of both defects in a wideband excitation mode (d).

Figure 6. Effect of the higher-order LDR: image of a square insert in CFRP plate at fundamental LDR (8980 Hz) (a), higher-order LDR (15600 Hz (b)), (27250 Hz (c)), and in a wideband (1-100 kHz) excitation mode (d).

nances are closer to the contour parts of the inset (Fig. 6, b) and gradually fill complete area of the defect (Fig. 6, c). As a result, the wideband excitation which covers a number of the higher-order LDR visualizes clearly a total shape of the defect (Fig. 6, d).

LDR defect imaging in thermosonics

In this section, the enhancement of a defect ultrasonic response by using the concept of LDR demonstrated above is applied to thermosonic imaging of defects. Conventional ultrasonic piezo-ceramic transducers (Conrad Elektronik GmbH) were used for excitation of defects in the strip-like specimens of 10-20 cm length. In larger specimens, the defects were activated by using mobile vacuum attached transducers (SI Scientific Instr. GmbH). In all experiments, acoustic power was monitored with a laser vibrometer and kept within mW-range.

Figures 7 & 8 show the results of LDR thermosonic imaging of the square insert in CFRP specimen, whose LDR laser vibrometry results were shown above in Fig. 6. Fig. 7 demonstrates a crucial role of LDR: At fundamental LDR frequency (8980 Hz) for 10 s insonation and 80 V input, the temperature response (~ 0.25 K) is more than an order of magnitude higher than that outside the defect resonance (8000 Hz).

Figure 7. Temperature response of a rectangular insert in CFRP plate at LDR frequency (8980 Hz, upper curve) and outside resonance (lower curve, 8000Hz).

The laser vibrometry measurements in this specimen reveal both the fundamental (Fig. 8, a; 8980 Hz) and the higher-order (Fig. 8, b; 15600 Hz) LDR with substantially different vibration patterns.

Figure 8. Laser vibrometry (a, b) and thermosonic (c, d) images of a square insert in CFRP plate at: fundamental LDR frequency (8980 Hz, (a, c)) and higher-order LDR (15600Hz, (b, d)).

Similar to the results on LDR laser vibrometry, the thermal images taken at the corresponding excitation frequencies (Fig. 8, c, d) demonstrate an importance of the higher-order resonances for visualization of the shape of the defect: while the fundamental LDR visualizes the center part, the higher-order LDR are responsible for imaging of the border areas of the defect.

Another example of LDR thermosonics in composites is given in Figs. 9 & 10 for point-like impact damage in CFRP plate ($270 \times 40 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$). The acoustic frequency response of the defect (Fig. 9, a) reveals fundamental LDR around 110 kHz. Unlike a smooth LDR frequency response for a "solid" defect like FBH (Fig. 2, a), the resonance curve for impact damage displays ripples associated with resonances of weakly coupled parts of the defect. This effect is also evident in the thermal frequency response (Fig. 9, b).

Figure 9. Acoustic (a) and thermal (b) LDR frequency responses of an impact induced damage in CFRP plate.

The temperature rise measured in Fig. 10, b confirms highly efficient LDR thermosonics of impact damage in CFRP: $\Delta T = 1.4$ K for ~ 60 mW input acoustic power. Such a temperature variation provides an opportunity for reliable LDR thermosonic imaging in mW power range (Fig. 10, a) with a high temperature contrast in lateral direction (Fig. 10, b).

The results shown above imply that a strong increase in the defect temperature rise (thermal output signal) at LDR frequency enhances the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of thermosonic imaging. On the other hand, an increase of SNR is also known to occur in the lock-in mode primarily due to diminishing noise level [5].

Figure 10. LDR thermosonic imaging of $\sim(5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2)$ impact damage area in a CFRP plate (a); quantified lateral temperature contrast of the image (b).

By introducing the benefit of LDR in the lock-in approach a resonance thermosonic mode operating at unusually low excitation levels can be projected. To this end, following the general lock-in concept the amplitude of ultrasonic excitation at the LDR frequency was modulated sinusoidally at lock-in frequency (between 0.01 Hz and 1 Hz). A temperature image sequence of the surface was recorded with the IR-camera and a discrete Fourier transformation at the lock-in-frequency was applied to compress this image sequence into a pair of amplitude and phase images.

An enhancement in sensitivity and the SNR of the LDR lock-in imaging are readily seen from Fig. 11, where the phase lock-in (a) and LDR temperature (b) thermosonic images of a FBH in PMMA plate are shown. To have the $\text{SNR} > 1$ in the conventional temperature image (Fig. 11, b), the input power had to be increased up to $\sim 1.8 \text{ mW}$ (to generate $\Delta T \sim 100 \text{ mK}$). On the contrary, the phase LDR lock-in image in Fig. 11, a) was taken when the input was reduced to anomalously low power of $\sim 170 \mu\text{W}$. The background for such an extraordinary performance is a combined action of the lock-in (reduction of noise) and the high thermosonic quality factor (efficient heat generation) in the LDR mode.

In Fig. 12, a, b, the enhancement in sensitivity of thermosonics by combining LDR and lock-in is illustrated for an impact damage in CFRP plate: the phase lock-in image (a) corresponds to $\sim 1 \text{ mW}$ input power while a similar contrast of the temperature image (b) requires $\sim 16 \text{ mW}$ of acoustic power.

Figure 11. LDR thermosonic imaging of FBH in PMMA plate at LDR frequency 12480 Hz: (a) - phase lock-in (lock-in frequency 0.05 Hz) image (acoustic input $\sim 170 \mu\text{W}$); (b) - temperature image at input power $\sim 1.8 \text{ mW}$.

Figure 12. LDR thermosonic imaging of an impact ($\sim 5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$) in CFRP plate: phase lock-in image (a) at $\sim 1 \text{ mW}$ input acoustic power; (b) - temperature image at $\sim 16 \text{ mW}$ input power.

LDR shearography

A conventional out-of-plane optical sensor head [6] with continuous-wave laser was used for time-averaged shearographic imaging. In Fig. 13, the laser vibrometer and shearography images of a FBH vibration in PMMA specimen obtained at the fundamental LDR (7672 Hz) are compared. The fringe pattern (Fig. 13, a) clearly demonstrates that shearography is sensitive to the gradient of out-of-plane LDR displacement ("bell-like" function in Fig. 13, c) in the shearing (horizontal) direction.

The effect of LDR is further demonstrated in Figs. 14-16 for realistic defects in composite materials and structures. In Fig. 14, the LDR imaging results are

Figure 13. Sherographic (a) and laser vibrometer images (b (top view), c (side view)) of a FBH vibration in PMMA plate at fundamental LDR (7672 Hz).

shown for aluminium honeycomb structure (thickness 16 mm) with GFRP liners ($0.5 \times 100 \times 100 \text{ mm}^2$, Fig. 14, a) with several inclusions of resin and water. The ultrasonic excitation was carried out by conventional piezo-ceramic transducers (Conrad Elektronik GmbH) attached to the rear side of the structure. The laser vibrometry scan of the front side (Fig. 14, b) indicates LDR of one of the defects at 14940 Hz. The results of both shearographic (Fig. 15) and thermosonic imaging (Fig. 16) confirm substantial enhancement of the sensitivity of detection at the LDR frequency: the images practically disappear even at a minor frequency mismatch from the LDR frequency.

Figure 14. LDR vibrometric image (b) of an adhesion lack area in honeycomb structure (a).

Figure 15. LDR shearographic imaging of an adhesion lack area in honeycomb structure: the excitation frequencies are indicated on the images.

Figure 16. LDR thermosonic imaging of an adhesion lack area in honeycomb structure (Fig. 14, a): the excitation frequencies are indicated on the images.

To trace frequency selectivity of LDR shearographic imaging we used a set of three circular FBH in PMMA plate. For the plate thickness of 25.5 mm, the depths of the holes changed from 22 to 24 mm thus defining different LDR frequencies and driving excitation frequencies, respectively. The images of the defects obtained by laser vibrometry, ultrasonic thermography and shearography at corresponding LDR frequencies are compared in Fig. 17. They confirm maximum sensitivity at the LDR frequencies; a minor variation of the frequencies is caused by different clamping conditions of the specimens.

Conclusions

In summary, the frequency match between the excitation ultrasonic frequency and the frequency of LDR results in substantial “amplification” of the defect vibration amplitude. It leads to enhancement of sensitivity and efficiency in ultrasonic NDT and imaging of defects via laser vibrometry, thermosonics and shearography. A strong frequency selectivity of LDR also results in opportunity of detecting a certain defect among multitude of the others by using all above mentioned NDT methods. An improvement of image quality is obtained in the higher-order LDR and wide-band ultrasonic excitation modes. The LDR NDT requires much lower acoustic power to activate the defects that makes it possible to avoid high-power ultrasonic instrumentation in both ultrasonic thermography and shearography.

Acknowledgement

The author acknowledges support of this study in the framework of ALAMSA project funded from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 314768.

Figure 17. LDR thermosonic (left), shearographic (center) and laser vibrometer (right) images of three FBH in PMMA specimen: the frequencies of maximum output are indicated on the images.

References

- [1] de Jong, N., Hoff, L., *Ultrasonics* Vol., 31, (1993), 175–181.
- [2] Rokhlin, S., *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, Vol., 69, (1981), 922-928.
- [3] Solodov, I., Bai, J., Bekgulyan, S., Busse, G., *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol., 99, (2011) 211911.
- [4] Solodov, I., Bai, J., Busse, G., *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol., 113 (2013), 223512.
- [5] Busse, G., Wu, D., Karpen, W., *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol., 71, (1992), 3962-3965.
- [6] Menner, Ph., Gerhard, H., Busse, G., *AIP Conference Proceedings*, Vol., 1211, Issue 1, (2010), 2068-2072.